

Transceiver Guidelines for Energy-Efficient Horseshoes Based on Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing

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Abstract: In filterless horseshoe networks, DSCM enables point-to-multipoint communications and granular control over bandwidth resources. By analyzing various volumes of traffic and typical intraday behavior, we provide guidelines for energy-efficient DSCM-transceiver deployments compared to single-carrier solutions. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Telecom operators are motivated by growing traffic demands [1] to continuously upgrade their optical networks to ensure coping with the forecast traffic growth and providing a robust infrastructure, all while adopting new technological solutions [2]. High-performing communication systems, besides delivering staggering data rates, must operate efficiently [3]. Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) [4], which is a transmission scheme where high-speed optical signals are constructed of lower-speed Digital Subcarriers (DSCs), represents a technology capable of improving the footprint of optical networks through the reduction of transceivers thanks to the deployment of Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) architectures. Moreover, an inherent flexibility aspect, i.e., dynamic allocation of DSCs, can be exploited to further optimize how the resources of the Transceivers (TRxs) are utilized: unnecessary DSCs could be deactivated to save on bandwidth and energy resources. Our previous work focused on hardware optimization in filterless networks [5]; now, we strive to provide a guideline for the power consumption of DSCM-capable TRx in horseshoe network topologies, focusing on how they behave under different traffic conditions, as well as the necessary manufacturing conditions for energy-efficient pluggable units.

2. Network description

Our study focuses on horseshoe-based metro-aggregation networks (see Fig. 1 (a)), where a hub node serves as interface between the access and the metro-regional segments of the network. This site connects to a series of leaf nodes, which aggregate traffic from customers. Here, the network scenario consists of 16 leaf nodes separated by fiber segments with lengths according to a Gamma distribution ($\alpha=2.4$; $\beta=0.3$; Avg.=14.5 km). To avoid additional in-line amplification, the maximum segment distance was capped to 80 km.

Fig. 1: (a) Network diagram of a filterless horseshoe with 16 leaf nodes (without protection path). (b) Intraday traffic profile for customer/home office. (c) TRx power dissipation as a function of data rate, and number of active DSCs. Data from 100G single-carrier (SC) units as reference.

The node architecture follows a dual-fiber filterless approach [5], where splitters are used in the downlink scenario (dashed magenta line) and couplers, in the uplink direction (solid dark blue line). At the leaf nodes, some Traffic Volume (TV), determined by a Gamma distribution ($\alpha=2.9$; $\beta=0.3$; Avg.=7.8 Gb/s), enters the network. Furthermore, we assume that the network's traffic follows a time-dependent behavior (Fig. 1 (b)). A communication scheme such as DSCM, where the DSCs can be treated as independent channels, offers the possibility to adjust the operation of the TRx, allowing operators to utilize hardware and spectral resources more efficiently. In turn, this characteristic enables establishing connections according to a P2MP scheme, where a single TRx communicates with multiple units simultaneously. Our study assumes that the DSCs transmit at 25 Gb/s (dual-polarized 4 GBd 16-QAM) and that there are two types of TRx: a 400G 16-DSC for the hub node and a lower-speed 100G variant exclusively for the leaf nodes. In addition, the DSCM-capable modules allow a flexible

rate adjustment through the (de-)activation of DSCs. The dependency between power consumption of the TRx and the number of active DSCs is depicted in Fig. 1 (c); the colored area symbolizes the range of values used in our simulation, while the colored markers, the maximum and minimum consumption considered. The relative consumption of these data points is estimated from Application-specific Integrated Circuits (ASIC) measurements [6]. In addition, the dashed and dotted lines represent reference SC pluggables [7].

3. Numerical results

To evaluate the network scenario under different traffic loads, the Overall Traffic Volume (OTV) of the network (i.e., the sum of the 16 individual TVs) is multiplied by a numerical factor. Knowing the amount of traffic and its behavior throughout the day, we can estimate how many TRx units are required to cover the demands effectively, as well as the precise number of DSCs that guarantee connectivity across all nodes. Due to the statistical nature of the TVs and the fiber segments, we have run our numerical analysis for a total of 500 networks for each OTV condition.

Fig. 2: Avg. power savings for DSCM-capable TRx w.r.t. to point-to-point 100G SC units as function of OTV.

For future network deployments, by optimizing the energy consumption of DSCM-capable TRx, there are considerable savings to be achieved even at transceiver level. Figure 2 shows the average energy savings (intraday) for the various OTVs as a function of the power dissipation of the DSCM-capable TRx w.r.t. to point-to-point scenarios where the 100G SC pluggables consume 5 W (top row) and 6 W (bottom row) per unit. The surface plots allow us to gauge horseshoe topologies and redirect expectations in accordance with hardware specifications. Moreover, P2MP and DSCM impact savings in different domains. For instance, reducing the number of ports/interfaces needed at the routers directly impacts faceplate usage and how these devices need to be provisioned and operated. However, an analysis of this magnitude is not within the scope of the current study.

4. Conclusions

Network deployments using DSCM enable a high degree of flexibility, reconfigurability, and energy-efficiency through the (de-)activation of DSCs when these are not required. By comparing the energy consumption of P2MP DSCM-based deployments w.r.t. point-to-point SC systems, we provide a design and manufacturing reference to guide the development of DSCM-capable TRx and create awareness of the potential operative savings.

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